

Code Book and Condensations of the Static Validation Study

Moderator: Author 1

Subjects: Practitioners of the R&D initiative

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This section presents an overview of the six practitioners who participated in the focus group. It also contains the transcriptions and codes involved in the static validation study. We include the explanation of our approach and the discussion with the participants.

Participants

In the following table we show an overview of the participant characterization. It is possible to observe that all participants had more than 2 years of experience working with ML and participated in at least 2 of such projects.

Id	Role	Project	# years	# ML projects
P1	Data Scientist	A	6	8
P2	Data Scientist	B	2	2
P3	Data Scientist	B	2	3
P4	Developer	A	2	4
P5	Developer	B	3	2
P6	Project Lead	A	2	2

We used the column 'Id' of Table I to identify the participants and their opinions. The moderator (M) of the focus group was the first author of the paper. We highlighted with color green the part of the text which contributes to generating the codes.

We translated the focus group to English. In the following, we outline the research questions of this study and present the transcriptions of the focus group.

Research Questions

- **RQ1:** What problems do participants face in practice when specifying ML-enabled systems?
- **RQ2:** What perception do the participants have of the retroactive specifications of projects A and B derived from PerSpecML v1?
- **RQ3:** What are the limitations and opportunities for improvement of PerSpecML v1?
- **RQ4:** To what extent do the participants perceive PerSpecML v1 as easy to use, useful and usable in the future?

Code Book

We identified the following list of codes attached to the transcription.

Code	Description	Type	RQ
LACKAPPR	Lack of approaches for supporting requirements for ML	Challenge	RQ1
OTHERAPPR	Other techniques for supporting requirements for ML	Challenge	RQ1
UNREALEXP	Unrealistic expectations of customers	Challenge	RQ1
MAPPEDACT	Relevant activities mapped by the diagram	Perception	RQ2
GUIDEVPROC	The Approach as a guide during the development process	Perception	RQ2
ENHANCEDCLA	Enhanced clarity	Perception	RQ2
MEANFULREL	Meaningful relationships	Perception	RQ2
IDHIDDENCON	Identify hidden concerns	Perception	RQ2
HELPCOM&DOC	Help to document and communicate with other stakeholders	Perception	RQ2
NEEDFOREX	Need for experimentation	Improvement	RQ3

ADDDOMAINEXP	Add domain expert as a stakeholder	Improvement	RQ3
PROVADDGUID	Provide additional guidance	Improvement	RQ3
SIMPLIFYTASK	Simplify some tasks	Improvement	RQ3
CLASSIFYCON	Classify concerns	Improvement	RQ3
IMPROVEREL	Improve relationships between tasks and concerns	Improvement	RQ3
IMPROVEUX	Improve user interfaces of the approach	Improvement	RQ3

Code Condensations

Id	Comment	Code
M	<p>If you don't understand some of the elements of PerSpecML (diagram + template), please let me know how I can help you. I can go back and explain again.</p> <p><i>[Here, we introduce to the participants some concepts about requirements engineering (RE) and machine learning (ML), and we detail our solution proposal called PerSpecML]</i></p> <p>Now we want to hear from you about requirements in the context of ML-enabled systems. Based on your experience, what problems/challenges do you face when specifying ML-enabled systems?</p>	
P6	<p>I've been working for just over 2 years with ML systems. I'm not an expert, but to the best of my knowledge, there is a lack of tools and methods that help in understanding and detailing these types of requirements. My feeling is that solution proposals of this type do not reach the industry. This leads to mismatches between practitioners and literature.</p>	LACKAPPR
P3	<p>I agree with P6, in my opinion, there is a lack of approaches following this line. I've never seen a standard or guideline shedding light on how to specify and document ML-enabled systems.</p>	LACKAPPR
P2	<p>From my side, I see lean inceptions as the closest thing to requirements for ML. I know this approach is not focused on ML-based</p>	OTHERAPPR

	systems, but in my opinion it has worked well. I also know that it has limitations, but this could be improved.	
P4	I'm curious to see a formal specification of an ML component. Based on my experience, these definitions are informal and emerge as the project progresses.	LACKAPPR
P5	Sometimes I feel that the ML development team often transmits skepticism to customers, not because of the lack of knowledge of its members, but because of the lack of an established process to define what can be done in ML terms with what the customer makes available, for example, in terms of data and business information.	LACKAPPR
M	Does anyone have any comments?	
P4	ML is a process of continuous experimentation. This is well known. Requirements could not be different in this context. I see that the process of designing an ML-enabled system is based on empirical knowledge, which makes it highly dependent on trial-and-error experimentation . At the beginning of the projects, initial requirements are defined, but at the end of the project these requirements are very different. As projects progress, these requirements change. I think this uncertainty could be reduced to avoid reworks.	NEEDFOREX
P1	<p>I see the involvement of key roles as a big problem in ML projects. Typically domain experts are busy, so they tend to be less involved in the early phases of ML projects. In the end, they often find unexpected results. Their involvement is important in areas such as feature engineering, data pre-processing and model evaluation.</p> <p>In that direction, I would like to mention that the diagram does not consider an important stakeholder in all the process. That stakeholder is the domain expert. This role is extremely important because they are essential to help define good objectives and to analyze data. The domain expert cannot be left out.</p> <p>Many times I worked as a domain expert of ML projects. So, If this role is not modeling in the diagram, I could not use it. Do you understand my point?</p>	ADDDOMAINEXP
P4	In addition, I think that customers often overestimate what ML can do . Most of the time, they expect that ML systems can solve all the problems. They also don't imagine the number of components that are required to operate and maintain an ML model over time. Requirements engineering could help to address these challenges	UNREALEXP

P6	I feel that the ML development team often transmits skepticism to customers, not because of the lack of knowledge of its members, but because of the lack of an established process to define what can be done in ML terms with what the client makes available.	LACKAPPR
M	I did not understand your point. What do you mean with “what can be done in ML terms with what customers make available”. Could you give some examples?	
P6	Sure, I mean, customers give us many files with data and verbal information about the business. But, what can we do with this to better align these recursos with what customers want to do?	
M	Ok. Let's talk about the requirements specifications of Project A and B that were presented several minutes ago that were built from two artifacts: the first was the perspective-based ML task and concern diagram, and the second was the specification template. Feel free to mention anything you consider important or relevant, but also any component that you consider could be improved or that was not clear.	
P4	I found the artifacts super interesting. In my view, the way we work is well mapped in the diagram. I can clearly see definitions of the ML project, model and data requirements, and user experiences aspects that typically I dont concern.	MAPPEDACT
P1	Looking at the diagram and its corresponding specifications allowed me to get an early overview of the requirements that can be refined as the project progresses. It is like a high-level guided development	GUIDEVPROC
P1	In addition, I found that the specifications facilitated a better understanding of the systems' functionality, components, and data requirements, specially for Project A, in which I was involved	ENHANCEDCLA
P6	In that line, identifying the tasks and concerns and their relationships allows identifying dependencies and influences as intended	ENHANCEDCLA
P3	I really liked the focus on diverse aspects such as data, model, and infrastructure. This landscape facilitates the understanding of the projects	ENHANCEDCLA
P6	I think the approach maps well the process that we follow in the company. Really the content is quite extensive, a lot of information, but also mapped the ML process, the flow is very interesting. By looking at the task-concern relationships, I was able to identify dependencies and influences as intended. I think that's clear.	MEANFULREL
P3	I consider these perspectives and the overview provided by the diagram very useful. I'm thinking: normally at the beginning of our ML projects, the team focuses on well-known requirements such as understanding the problem to be solved, obtaining data, and some	IDHIDDENREQ

	<p>performance metrics that the model must achieve. Just that. As the team faces ML tasks, concerns arise that are not considered at the beginning of the projects. This can negatively impact project management. So I think this overview of ML that provides the approach is cool. For example, Typically, user experience concerns are put in the background. With PerSpecML was possible to early specify forcefulness, a concern analyzed late in the validation phase of Project B.</p>	
P5	<p>Let me understand something. The idea is the following: if someone is working within an ML project, someone has to read the perspective diagram and then fill the specification template, right?</p>	
M	<p>Yes, the purpose of the diagram is to allow requirements engineers or other professionals in charge of these functions, analyzing the different tasks and concerns from each perspective so that they can be analyzed with the different stakeholders. With this, the ML specification template can be filled with the components that apply.</p>	
P5	<p>Ok, In my opinion, it is easy to convey the specifications to stakeholders, enabling better collaboration and alignment throughout the development process. For example, as a developer I can identify tasks where I need to collaborate with data scientists. That's cool! I consider this resource of the approach very important. In many times, collaborative work is essential to be successful and achieve the value of what is planned. In ML projects this should be mandatory since multidisciplinary teams need to communicate well.</p>	HELPCOM&DOC
P1	<p>From what I've seen, looking at the ML diagram allowed me to have an overview of the requirements that can be analyzed from the early stages of the project and the requirements that are defined as the project progresses. But I have one doubt. Did you ever consider a roadmap to follow the diagram? For example: it would be nice to have a step-by-step, activity enumeration, template filling flow of the approach.</p>	PROVADDGUID
P2	<p>I agree with P1. It is not clear to me what is the order of execution of the diagram. A roadmap would be very important to give an idea to those involved in the project about the activities that later on will have to be attended by X or Y professionals. So I see this diagram as a planner that can help ML teams identify upcoming tasks. But for that, you need to have a roadmap that allows you to map what is done first, what dependencies there are, what are the possible paths.</p>	PROVADDGUID
P5	<p>I also have suggestions. In my opinion the diagram needs to simplify some tasks. In the model perspective, the number of tasks seems large in practice, perhaps it would be interesting to reduce the format.</p>	SIMPLIFYTASK

P3	<p>Another point I would like to highlight is the following. I've worked on several projects developing the dashboards combining predictions and preferences of customers and end-users. Typically, I see user experience requirements take a back seat. Okay, we make an effort to identify some requirements at the beginning of the projects, but that's not enough in my opinion. The relevance of user experience in the success of this type of system forces us to reconsider this.</p>	MAPPEDACT
P5	<p>I agree with P3 but in the case of the ML objective perspective. I also understand the need to consider data, model, user and infrastructure, but in my opinion, the functional behavior of ML models, which is reflected in the goals and objectives, is crucial. I think that perspective is really the starting point of everything. This is where the team must really understand what the customer wants to determine how ML can help them to achieve their goals.</p>	MAPPEDACT
P6	<p>I have a suggestion regarding the distribution of some tasks and concerns of the diagram. Look at the ML objective perspective. The 'define ML objectives' task has independent concerns that could be part of separate tasks. In my opinion the leading indicators are not goals but are important metrics to achieve the objectives.</p>	IMPROVEREL
M	<p>This feedback is very important for us. Now, regarding improvements, elements of the artifacts that are not clear, feel free to mention and express your ideas.</p>	
P4	<p>Well, an ML project involves many activities, both technical and non-technical. I think this could be reflected in the artifacts and made clearer, as differentiating the types of tasks, concerns in this case, helps to better address the responsibilities of those involved.</p>	CLASSIFYCON
P2	<p>When you introduced the specification of the projects, to be honest, I didn't like the template so much. In my opinion, the specification template is very simple, I mean, it does not have relationships or related tasks like the diagram.</p> <p>Regarding the completeness of tasks and concerns, I feel that maybe something is missing. I don't know exactly what's missing, I just keep thinking that ML is a discipline that involves many areas such as mathematics, statistics, engineering... so it would be good for you to review and evaluate if something is missing.</p>	IMPROVEUX
M	<p>I agree with your point of view. In fact, the scope of our work did not consider dividing or differentiating this issue from technical tasks. An improvement of the approach could consider this. Thanks.</p>	

	<p>Now we are going to fill out a questionnaire where you can mention the main benefits and limitations of using our approach. With this we also want to validate what was said here. Any questions please let me know.</p>
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